

Engaging Patients with Diabetes Using a Mobile Application

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Background

- Diabetes is associated with a 75% ↑mortality rate in adults compared to those without diabetes.
- U.S. adults who attained glycemic control, (HbA1c <7%) was 50.5% from 2015 to 2018.
- Poor glycemic control is associated with an increase in morbidity and mortality.

Purpose

To evaluate if a mobile application (One Drop) improves glycemic control and engagement in adults with diabetes with an HbA1c >7%

Methods

Setting: Outpatient endocrinology clinic
Recruitment: In person and flyers
Participants: 12 patients with diabetes & HbA1c >7%
 • 9 Male, 3 Female
 • Age 29 - 67 years
 • Years with DM <1 to 30 years
Measures: Demographic survey, pre and post-intervention HbA1c & Altarum Consumer Engagement (ACE) measure, Satisfaction and Usability Survey, active use

Conceptual Framework

Patient Activation Model

Results

- Pre-Post ACE**
- Commitment 16.0, 16.0
 - Informed Choice 13.1, 14.5
 - Navigation 16.3, 18.8

Active use 8/12 (67%)

Mean HbA1c ↓: Pre 9.1% Post 8.1%

High Satisfaction & Usability scores (Highest score=3)

Limitations

- Small # of participants
- Short implementation period
- Seasonal variations
- COVID-19 pandemic
- Technological glitches

Conclusions

- Using a mobile app (One Drop) as part of the treatment plan can increase patient engagement & improve glycemic control in patients with diabetes
- Patients found the app easy to use, helpful, and recommended it for other patients

Recommendations

- Mobile technology is a useful resource in the management of diabetes and should be integrated in practice.
- Mobile technology may also be useful in the management of other chronic conditions.

References

